

TYPES OF DEIXIS AND THEIR PRAGMATIC FUNCTIONS IN EVERYDAY COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: It can be said that the relationship between language and context is best manifested through the concept of deixis. It refers to a set of expressions whose interpretation depends on the context in which they appear. The current study tries to present a thorough review of the topic in question from a pragmatic perspective, enhancing its different categories, functions, and shedding some light on its relation to the phenomenon of indexicality. Deixis has not been given its due attention. Thus, this study attempts to bridge this gap in the literature through answering the following questions: What are the categories of deixis? What is the role of context in interpreting deixis? And what is the relation between deixis and indexicality? This survey eventually reveals that deixis has to do with the connection between context and the speaker's communicative intention.

Key words: deixis, pragmatics, context, proximal, distal, gestural and symbolic deixis, indexicality

HAR KUNI ALOQADA DEIKSIS TURLARI VA ULARNING PRAGMATIK FUNKTSIYALARI

Annotatsiya: Til va kontekst o'rtasidagi munosabat deiks tushunchasi orqali eng yaxshi namoyon bo'ladi. Bu talqinligi ular paydo bo'lgan kontekstga bog'liqligini anglatadi. Hozirgi o'qish pragmatik nuqtai nazardan mavzuni sinchkovlik bilan ko'rib chiqishga, uning turli xil toifalarini, funktsiyalarini kuchaytiradi va indeksiallik fenomeniga nisbatan bir oz yorug'likni to'kib borishga harakat qiladi. Deiksga e'tibor berilmagan. Shunday qilib, ushbu tadqiqot quyidagi savollarga javob berish orqali adabiyotda bu bo'shliqni ko'paytirishga harakat qiladi: deikslarning toifalari nimada? Deiksni sharhlashda kontekstning roli nima? Deikin va indeksi-indeksi o'rtasidagi munosabat nimada? Ushbu so'rov oxir-oqibat deiks kontekst va karnayning kommunikativ niyatlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik bilan bog'liqligini aniqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: deiksis, pragmatika, kontekst, proksimal, distal, gestlom va ramziy dehis.

ТИПЫ DEIXIS И ИХ ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЕ ФУНКЦИИ В ПОВСЕДНЕВНОМ ОБЩЕНИИ

Аннотация: Можно сказать, что отношения между языком и контекстом лучше всего проявляются через концепцию Deixis. Это относится к набору выражений, интерпретация которого зависит от

контекста, в котором они появляются. Текущее исследование пытается представить тщательный обзор рассматриваемой темы с прагматической точки зрения, повышая ее различные категории, функции и проливая некоторый свет на ее отношение к явлению индексности. Deixis не уделял должного внимания. Таким образом, это исследование пытается преодолеть этот пробел в литературе, отвечая на следующие вопросы: Каковы категории Deixis? Какова роль контекста в интерпретации Deixis? И какова связь между Deixis и индексированностью? Этот опрос в конечном итоге показывает, что Deixis имеет отношение к связи между контекстом и коммуникативным намерением говорящего.

Ключевые слова: deixis, прагматика, контекст, проксимальный, дистальный, геестурный и символический Deixis, индексность.

Introduction

Some sentences of English are almost impossible to be understood without knowing the context in which they occur. For example: They'll have to do that tomorrow, because they aren't here now. It can be seen that out of context this sentence is extremely vague. This is due to the fact that it includes a large number of deictic expressions (they, that, tomorrow, here, now) whose interpretation depends on the immediate physical context in which they are spoken. These expressions are very obvious instances of bits of language which can only be understood in terms of the speaker's meaning (Yule, 1985: p. 99).

Cruse (2006: p. 44) suggest that deictic terms constitute a subcategory of definite referring expressions. Moreover, usage of the term deixis varies, but most naturally it describes referring expressions which refer to the location of the speaker as a referent point or deictic centre. An example is the use of this and that. In Can you pass that newspaper, the newspaper specified is typically fairly distant from the speaker. Nevertheless, as soon as the speaker obtains the newspaper, another reference to it will involve a different deictic element, I'm going to have to stop buying this newspaper. Such change is a characteristic of a deictic expression.

It is asserted that deixis assumes a principal place in the study of context due to the fact that it represents the solitary most noticeable way in which the speech settings is encoded in language structure itself. Such expressions appear in all human languages and possess a number of fascinating features that set them apart from other interactive resources, verbal and nonverbal. It is assumed that as long as language is basic to human sociality, deixis is basic to language through its capability of constituting both subjects and objects (Hanks, 2005: p. 191).

Deixis, the phenomena of requiring contextual information to create the meaning of a phrase

The role of context in helping to determine reference, essentially language, concerns with the ways in which the interpretation of utterance depends on the analyses of the context of utterance. That's why deixis deals with the connection between discourse and the situation in which discourse is used. The term of

“deixis” is used from the Greek word which means “ to show” or ‘to indicate’, used to denote the elements in a language which refer directly to the situation.

According to Yule, in English Language (1996, p.93), there are three different ways to point out in. they are gesture, symbolic and anaphoric¹.

- “Gesture” is used by which it can be properly interpreted only by somebody who is monitoring some physical aspects of communication situation. Gestural deixis refers, broadly, to deictic expressions whose understanding requires some sort of audio-visual information. A simple example is when an object is pointed at and referred to as ‘this’ or ‘that’. However, the category can include other types of information than pointing, such as direction of gaze, tone of voice, and so on.

eg. I want you to copy this document.

- “Symbolic” use of deictic expression means that the interpretation involves merely knowing certain aspects of speech communication situation, whether this knowledge comes by common perception or not.

eg. I want you to copy this document there.

- “Anaphoric” is the use of expression that can be correctly interpreted by knowing what other portions of the same discourse that expression is co-referential with an anaphoric use of an expression, which can be seen in the sentence.

eg. I have copy the document and I put it there.

If we refer the theory of Stephan Levinson is included:

a) Person Deixis

It stipulates what is a deictic reference to the participant role of a referent such as:

- The Speaker (The utter of a message. Deictic center of his/her own deictic references), Levinson 1983.

2- The addressee.

- The Referents which are neither speaker nor addressee.

The Deictic center is a reference point in relation to which a deictic expression is to be interpreted. The deictic center is also most typically the present time, location, participant role and so forth of speaker.

Conclusions

The theoretical background and different text analysis in this research converge in an updated definition about role and importance of using deixis in today’s communication. Literature and other forms of written communications need assessment with points of reference particularly in the way communications are developed in our global, multilayered and multicultural society

In this context, Deixis is one of the most important notion in general linguistics and is a vital link between the real life environment around us (time-frame, physical location, people involved etc.) and what we actually say (the utterance, linguistic terms).Deixis as a engine researcher by many pragmatists focuses on phrase meaning and being the heart of reference research as widely

known literature in semantics and pragmatics demonstrating a great dimension between two major fields: Semantics and Pragmatics.

Deixis concerns ways in each languages encode of descriptive context or grammatical features of the context of utterance or speech event, and thus also concerns ways in which the interpretation of utterances depends on the analysis of that context of utterance.

According to the deixis analyses focused on importance of the word meaning, what is intended to convey when using a range of word, the various kinds of communication made possible by language. Speaker's meaning is what a speaker means when he uses a piece of language.

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